

Gluconate Complexes of Er(III), Tm(III), Yb(III) and Lu(III)

C. PANDA and R. K. PATNAIK

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Rourkela-769 008.

Manuscript received 26 March 1979, accepted 6 October 1979

The equilibrium constants for the formation of complexes by the rare earth metal ions Er^{3+} , Tm^{3+} , Yb^{3+} and Lu^{3+} with Gluconic acid have been determined by pH-potentiometric method.

KOSTROMINA¹ has determined the instability constants of the cationic rare earth gluconates in the pH range 2-3 by potentiometric and ion exchange method. The present paper deals with the determination of the formation constants of doubly charged cationic complex at low pH and its dissociation to other complexes at higher pH.

Experimental

99.99% pure nitrates of Er(III), Tm(III), Yb(III) and Lu(III) were obtained from Research Organic/Inorganic Chemical Corporation, Sheldon Street, Sunvale, California. Since the reaction of gluconic acid with the rare earth metal ions was found to be slow, the solutions were allowed to stand for 48 hrs in an atmosphere of nitrogen and their pH was measured with a digital pH meter (ECI-822A) at $32 \pm 1^\circ$. The constant ionic strength was maintained at 0.1 M by the addition of potassium nitrate.

Results and Discussion

The liberation of protons during the complex formation remains same when the metal-ligand ratio is

Fig 1. 0.1M Sodium hydroxide added, ml.

Fig. 1. pH titration of 50.00 ml of solution containing 5.0×10^{-3} g. mole of potassium nitrate and 3.125×10^{-4} g. mole of gluconic acid (Curve A) and that of the same volume of four other solutions each containing the same quantities of the above constituents and 2.5×10^{-4} g. mole of erbiumnitrate (Curve B₁), thuliumnitrate (Curve B₂), ytterbium nitrate (Curve B₃) and lutecium nitrate (Curve B₄) against 0.1M sodium hydroxide.

increased from 1:1 to 1:5. This indicates the formation of 1:1 complex. The reaction taking place in experiment-1 may be represented as

The charge of the complex, C, depends on the number of protons liberated, n. The value of n are calculated as followed in the cadmium citrate complex² and gluconate complexes of Y(III)³, Pr(III) and Nd(III)⁴, Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III)⁵ and tartrate complex of Y(III)⁶. The n values are >1 above pH 3.8, 3.8, 3.6 and 3.6 respectively for Er(III), Tm(III), Yb(III) and Lu(III). Assuming n to be one below these pH values, [C²⁺] is calculated as 'before'².

The equilibrium constants $-\log K$ (pK) of the reaction(1) are calculated and are found to be 0.36 ± 0.11 , 0.27 ± 0.13 , 0.20 ± 0.07 and 0.13 ± 0.05 respectively for Er(III), Tm(III), Yb(III) and Lu(III).

In the pH ranges, 4.0-5.4, 4.0-5.2, 3.8-5.0 and 3.8-5.0 respectively for Er(III), Tm(III), Yb(III) and Lu(III), n is > 1 but < 2. Hence the complex, C²⁺, dissociates according to the reaction(2)

The equilibrium constants $-\log K_1$ (pK₁) of the reaction(2) are calculated as followed in the citrate complex of cadmium and are found to be 5.27 ± 0.02 , 5.16 ± 0.04 , 5.08 ± 0.00 and 4.98 ± 0.00 for Er(III), Tm(III), Yb(III) and Lu(III) systems respectively.

In the pH ranges 5.60-8.25, 5.40-6.90, 5.20-9.17 and 5.20-7.23 respectively for Er(III), Tm(III) Yb(III) and Lu(III) systems respectively, the n values are > 2 but < 3, which indicates the dissociation of the complex, C⁺ by the equation(3),

The equilibrium constants, $-\log K_2$ (pK₂) of the reaction (3) are calculated as followed in the tartrate complex of manganese⁷ and are found to be, 6.15 ± 0.04 , 5.85 ± 0.04 , 5.21 ± 0.05 and 5.09 ± 0.02 for Er(III), Tm(III), Yb(III) and Lu(III) systems respectively. The

hydroxides of the metals are precipitated at pH 8.25, 6.90, 9.17 and 7.23 respectively for Er(III), Tm(III), Yb(III) and Lu(III).

Fig. 2 0.05M Na-gluconate added, ml.

Fig. 2. pH titration of 50.00 ml of solution containing 5.0×10^{-3} g. mole of potassium nitrate (Curve A) and that of the same volume of four other solutions each containing the same quantities of the above constituents and 2.5×10^{-4} g. mole of erbium nitrate (Curve B₁), thulium nitrate (Curve B₂), ytterbium nitrate (Curve B₃) and lutecium nitrate (Curve B₄) against 0.05M Na-gluconate.

In the experiment-2, fig. 2 the reaction taking place may be represented as

when the pH is decreased, the complex, C⁺, combines with a proton to form the complex C²⁺. Beyond the 1:1 metal-ligand ratio, the pH increases due to the addition of excess Na-gluconate and the complex, C²⁺ dissociates to C⁺ and H⁺. It can be shown as in the earlier investigation that

$$[TGl] - [M(NO_3)_3] = b[HGl]$$

where $b = 1 + \frac{k}{[H^+]}$ (k, the dissociation constant of gluconic acid³ = 2.75×10^{-4}) and [TGl] is the molar concentration of total gluconate.

$$[C^+] = [H^+] + [HGl] \text{ and } [C^{2+}] = [M(NO_3)_3] - [C^+]_{\text{obs}}$$

The equilibrium constants $-\log K_1$ of the reaction (2) are calculated as before and the values are found to be 5.21 ± 0.04 , 5.13 ± 0.03 , 5.04 ± 0.00 and 4.95 ± 0.00 for Er(III), Tm(III), Yb(III) and Lu(III) systems respectively. Below the 1:1 metal-ligand ratio, the ions, M³⁺, and C²⁺ are present. It can be shown that

$$[HGl] = \frac{[TGl] - [H^+] \left(1 + \frac{[H^+]}{K_1}\right)}{\left(1 + \frac{k}{[H^+]}\right) + \left(1 + \frac{[H^+]}{K_1}\right)}$$

$$[C^+] = [H^+] + [HGl] \text{ and } [C^{2+}] = \frac{[H^+]}{K_1} [C^+]$$

The equilibrium constants $-\log K_2$ of the reaction-4 are calculated as before and the values are found to be 2.58 ± 0.07 , 2.42 ± 0.16 , 2.30 ± 0.13 and 2.25 ± 0.10 for Er(III), Tm(III), Yb(III) and Lu(III) systems respectively.

It can also be shown that $K_2 \times k / K_1 = K$. The $-\log k_2 \times k / K_1$ values are found to be 0.87 ± 0.07 , 0.83 ± 0.16 , 0.78 ± 0.13 and 0.82 ± 0.10 for Er(III), Tm(III), Yb(III) and Lu(III) systems respectively which agree well with the respective values of K in experiment 1.

Fig. 3 Sodium hydroxide added, ml.

Fig. 3. pH titration of 50.00 ml of solution containing 5.0×10^{-3} g. mole of potassium nitrate and 1.25×10^{-3} g. mole of Na-gluconate (Curve A) and that of the four other solutions each containing the same quantities of the above constituents and 2.5×10^{-4} g. mole of erbium nitrate (Curve B₁), thulium nitrate (Curve B₂), ytterbium nitrate (Curve B₃) and lutecium nitrate (Curve B₄) against 0.1 M sodium hydroxide.

In the experiment-3 (Fig. 3) the metal-ligand ratio is nearly 1:5 and the formation of the complex is therefore assumed to be complete. It is observed in experiment-1 that the cationic complex C²⁺ dissociates to C⁺ and then to neutral complex C with the gradual increase of pH. Similar complexes will exist in the similar pH ranges in this experiment also. It can be shown according to the methods suggested in the manganese tartrate complex that

$$[C^+] = [H^+] + [NaOH] + \frac{[TGl] - [M(NO_3)_3]}{\left(1 + \frac{k}{[H^+]}\right)}$$

[C²⁺] is calculated by subtracting [C⁺] from [M(NO₃)₃].

The equilibrium constants $-\log K_1$ of the reaction-2 are calculated as before and are found to be 5.18 ± 0.03 , 5.06 ± 0.03 , 5.01 ± 0.04 and 4.80 ± 0.07 for Er(III), Tm(III), Yb(III) and Lu(III) systems respectively which agree well with the respective K_1 values in experiment-1.

The dissociation of the complex C^+ to C and H^+ takes place in the pH ranges 5.60–8.25, 5.40–6.90, 5.20–9.17 and 5.20–7.23 for Er(III)–Lu(III) systems respectively. It can be shown that

$$[C] = [H^+] + [NaOH] - [M(NO_3)_3] + \frac{[TGI] - [M(NO_3)_3]}{\left(1 + \frac{k}{[H^+]}\right)}$$

$[C^+]$ is calculated by subtracting $[C]$ from $[M(NO_3)_3]$. The equilibrium constants $-\log K_2$ are calculated and are found to be 6.56 ± 0.10 , 5.87 ± 0.02 , 5.79 ± 0.02 and 5.54 ± 0.07 for Er(III)–Lu(III) systems respectively which are very much similar to the respective K_2 values obtained in experiment-1.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the U.G.C., New Delhi and Govt. of India for research grants.

References

1. N. A. KOSTROMINA, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.* 1963, 8, 988.
2. R. K. PATNAIK and S. PANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 34, 673.
3. C. PANDA and R. K. PATNAIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 843.
4. C. PANDA and R. K. PATNAIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 1079.
5. C. PANDA and R. K. PATNAIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (In press).
6. K. K. TRIPATHY and R. K. PATNAIK, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, 35, 1050.
7. K. K. TRIPATHY and R. K. PATNAIK, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, 5, 511.
8. R. K. CANNAN and A. KIBRICK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2314.